

Evaluation of Nutritional Potential of Five Unexplored Wild Edible Food Plants from Eastern Himalayan Biodiversity Hotspot Region (India)

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Abstract : Wild edible food plants contain a number of organic phytochemical that have been linked to the promotion of good health. These plants used by the local people of Arunachal Pradesh (Northeast India) are found to have high nutritional potential to maintain general balance diet. A study was conducted to evaluate the nutritional potential of five commonly found, unexplored wild food plants namely, *Piper pedicellatum* C. DC (leaves), *Gonostegia hirta* (Blume ex Hassk.) Miq. (leaves), *Mussaenda roxburghii* Hook. f. (leaves), *Solanum spirale* Roxb. (leaves and fruits) and *Cyathea spinulosa* Wall. ex Hook. (pith portion and tender rachis) from East Siang District of Arunachal Pradesh Northeast (India) for ascertaining their suitability for utilization as supplementary food. Results of study revealed that *P. pedicellatum*, *C. spinulosa*, and *S. spirale* (leaves) are the most promising species which have high nutritional content out of the five wild food plants investigated which is required for the normal growth and development of human.

Keywords : wild edible plants, gross energy, *Gonostegia hirta*, *Cyathea spinulosa*

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